

Enhancing capabilities of in-operation new space EO satellites using embedded AI for object detection

Dr. Francois De Vieilleville⁽¹⁾, Nimesh Tahalooa⁽¹⁾, Nicolas-Marcel Lemoine⁽¹⁾, Dr. Andis Dembovskis⁽¹⁾, Bella Acevedo-Rodriguez⁽²⁾, Grant Schmaedick⁽²⁾

⁽¹⁾ *AGENIUM Space*

1 Avenue de l'Europe, Campus 1, Bâtiment A, 31400 TOULOUSE, FRANCE

Email: andis.dembovskis@agenium.com

⁽²⁾ *Loft Orbital*

45 Boulevard de Strasbourg, 31000 TOULOUSE, FRANCE

Email: bella.acevedo@loftorbital.com

ABSTRACT

AI on board is gaining traction as the need for a more efficient use of resources (downlink bandwidth) or a strong need of reactivity (quasi real time alerts) is shaping new missions and hardware needs. However, those missions have been more about using available HW to their utmost potential for EO use-cases than designing a specific system for a given purpose. Such diversity is possible with HW reconfiguration capabilities, particularly with SocFPGA HW type.

Within this logic we have pushed and applied this concept to bring AI capabilities on a satellite that was not designed to harbor one at the start. We will elaborate on what was done on ground for defining use cases, preparing the data, training the models and ensuring on board execution compatibility with given execution constrains. We will also give some numbers about the incremental procedure that was used to allow improvements on the DNN themselves ensuring operational capabilities within a very short time span. We elaborate on operational results and the potential benefits for EO missions.

Loft successfully integrated the AGENIUM Space's AI algorithm into its onboard payload interface and processing units, facilitating the efficient and segregated use of onboard resources. An autonomous pipeline has been developed to reprocess artifacts from the Simera imager payload using the AGENIUM's algorithm. We demonstrate that the latter is improving F1 score significantly. The autonomous ground products then delivered these AI outputs providing a substantial sample size that evaluated various modes from each software update.

Eventually we conclude that this work demonstrated that enabling AI on new space EO satellite can bring further value to existing missions and democratize the use of AI in space.

INTRODUCTION

The recent years have seen a boom in the number of satellites sent in orbit around Earth. The 26th version of the “Satellites to be Built and Launched” report by Euroconsult forecasts an average of over 2800 satellites to be launched annually over the next decade [1]. Among those satellites, some are dedicated to Earth Observation, transmitting visual data. What was once limited to low-resolution RGB imaging on a handful of satellites is now extended to high-resolution multi-band images, several dozens of bands in the case of hyperspectral imaging, on a larger number of satellites – a rise driven by the introduction of smallsats and cubesats [2]. This means that more data is available more frequently, requiring a greater downlink bandwidth and more on-board storage. However, a significant volume of data is unusable, due to seasonal reasons such as images consisting primarily of clouds or smoke, hiding objects of interest. Also, some use cases consist in finding small objects in large tiles. In those cases, the computing stations on ground must comb through a significant amount of meaningless data (water) to find the relevant objects. It would be more efficient to filter the data before downlink. Different solutions can be considered, such as using intermediate data hubs in orbit or directly integrating the selection process on the platform responsible for image acquisition. The latter has been implemented and is described in this paper. To achieve this goal, Agenium Space has developed a deep learning-based application to detect objects of interest (boats, clouds) on images captured by a SimeraSense optical sensor on board the YAM-3 satellite operated by Loft Orbital. The main challenge was to be able to develop algorithms which could perform well with limited computing power on a system not initially designed to run AI applications. Also, the satellite was already in orbit with a set computing payload, which increased the integration complexity. This mission shows that such tasks are feasible, and they can even be improved as new images are acquired.

This paper focuses on the data processing aspect of the mission. An overview of the hardware and execution environment is given before diving in the processing details, to give the context required to understand the choices detailed in the later sections. The data processing section is further subdivided into three parts. First, the use cases, along with the reasons for their selection, are defined. Then, an outline of the database creation process is given, followed by the training of the deep learning algorithms. The next section describes the software used to run those algorithms. The results, both in terms of detection scores and throughput, are presented. We conclude by listing the improvements that can be added in similar future missions. Some of those improvements have already since been developed by Agenium Space.

HARDWARE AND ENVIRONMENT

Such a complex mission requires the interaction of several components. It is therefore important to provide details about the execution environment, both in terms of hardware and software, to properly interpret the results. The YAM-3 satellite has a sun-synchronous orbit at an altitude of 520km. It contains an imaging sensor made by SimeraSense, the MonoScape100, which captures 3072 x 4096 panchromatic images with a ground sampling distance of 4.75m at the satellite’s altitude, under nadir-pointing conditions. The acquired image is fed directly to Agenium Space’s software, without applying any radiometric corrections. The computing payload is a Xilinx Zynq 7000 series System-on-Chip (SoC) comprised of a CPU and an FPGA (SoC-FPGA). An operating system, PetaLinux, provided by AMD Xilinx, along with the Vitis AI framework [3], facilitated the deployment of the object detection software. Concerning the version, Vitis AI 1.2 was chosen as it was the latest version supported by the on-board SoC. A crucial component of the Vitis AI package is the AMD Deep Learning Processing unit (DPU), a custom FPGA module dedicated to executing operations found in a neural network. The CPU handles the pre-processing and post-processing while the DPU handles the core processing. The next section will dive into the data processing details.

DATA PROCESSING

Use Cases

The primary goal of on-board processing is to reduce the volume of data sent to the ground. Therefore, objects of interest must be identified to establish the filtering criteria. Several aspects must be taken into consideration. These may include the value of the identified object (different missions will have varying objects of interest), the resolution of the imaging sensor or the availability of similar data used to train the neural networks.

Taking those conditions into account, one use case seems straightforward: the measure of the cloudiness of images. Clouds can appear on tiles around the globe and are less dependent on the resolution of the image. In most cases, clouds are unwanted and mask the actual objects being observed. The ability to identify cloudy tiles would greatly reduce the number of unwanted images downlinked. That is why we decided to go for cloud segmentation, i.e. the identification of clouds on a per-pixel basis.

Secondly, the imaging sensor has a resolution of 4.75m. To be able to detect an isolated object, it must span over several pixels and therefore be several tens of metres long and wide such as a 120m by 60m object. Large ships such as oil tankers, cargo ships and aircraft carriers fit this criterion. Smaller motorboats can also be detected while they are moving, thanks to their wake. Being able to pinpoint a ship in a particular region of the sea could accelerate the response time during an emergency for example. Agenium Space chose to identify boats both using a per-pixel approach (boat segmentation) and using a bounding-box approach (boat detection), to compare the two.

Dataset Preparation

Neural networks learn from existing data, mostly in a supervised way. In most cases, the data must be labelled, i.e. each element in the dataset has an associated class (boat and cloud in our case). For segmentation, each pixel of an image has an associated class whereas for detection, there are bounding boxes (a set of 4 coordinates) around the objects of interest, if any, for each image. The data must naturally be representative of that available on-board. They must have the same characteristics as the imaging sensor, as described in an earlier section. In our case, the satellite, being in orbit since 2020, had already acquired some images. These had to be labelled. To get the mission started as early as possible, labelled images from other sources were used and processed to create a dataset with the expected characteristics. The images were converted to grayscale and resized to match the MonoScape100's resolution. Different methods were tested to reproduce the MonoScape100's radiometry by matching the colour histograms or computing the mean and variance in the available images, then normalising the simulated images using those values. However, very few images were available initially to determine a reliable radiometric signature of the MonoScape100 images. The pixel values are highly dependent on the scene being observed (barren ground, forest, industrial zone, residential zone, oceans, clouds) and on the illumination (time of day, angle of observation). Therefore, the simplest method, normalising using the mean and variance, was used.

The dataset must eventually include the actual images. Various tools exist to assist in the labelling process. One such tool, Intelligently Reinforced Image Segmentation (IRIS), was designed by ESA-PhiLab [\[4\]](#). IRIS is an application with a graphical interface, specialising in the creation of Earth Observation segmentation datasets. This was deemed ideal for the cloud dataset, as the patches to label were large and had pixel values which did not vary much. A mask based on threshold values was generated using IRIS. The threshold value was defined as the value, close to saturation, from which there was the biggest jump in pixel count as this was the case with images which partially contain clouds. With some finetuning, this allowed to generate satisfactory masks for thick clouds. Thin clouds were harder to label, especially when they were above land. As an example, on the panchromatic band, it was difficult to distinguish between a dense forest and a blob of thin clouds since they both had a grainy veil-like texture. Worse results were obtained when including thin clouds. They were therefore excluded.

Regarding the boats dataset, the IRIS tool was not appropriate since the objects were very small. To overcome this issue, we decided to divide each image in multiple tiles, and then segment the boats found in those tiles. This meant that the boats would represent a significant portion of the region of interest. The first step made use of a prompt-based object detection tool developed by IDEA Research, called Grounding Dino [\[5\]](#). It generated bounding boxes around some boats. However, it also missed many, especially the less obvious ones (docked boats or motorboats). This was likely because Grounding Dino is not specialised for grayscale satellite images. Therefore, some manual labelling was required to complete the detection dataset. Following that, we leveraged a segmentation tool, segment-geospatial [\[6\]](#) based on SegmentAnything by Meta AI [\[7\]](#), to generate the masks around the boats in each previously identified bounding box.

The simulated dataset was thus gradually supplemented with images from the actual sensor. It was not completely replaced for the boats dataset because there were not enough boats in the MonoScape100 images already downlinked.

Training of the Neural Network

With the datasets ready, let us now dive in the process of creating the neural networks. The models used should be able to be implemented using operations supported by Vitis AI, while satisfying the on-board memory and power constraints. Transformers, due to their large size, were out of the question. Among convolutional neural networks, the U-Net architecture [8] performs well for segmentation use cases. On the other hand, for object detection, the Single-Shot Detection network (SSD) [9] is ideal since it involves a single pass to predict both the object localisation and class. Therefore, smaller models, inspired by these architectures, were designed.

Intuitively, one might suppose that, for a given architecture, larger models, having access to a greater number of features, are better predictors than their smaller counterparts. Furthermore, to improve predictions, a technique known as model ensembling is often used [10]. It consists in combining the predictions of multiple models, by averaging their outputs for example. Combining these two ideas leads to a technique called distillation where a smaller model (also called a student model) is fed both the ground truth and a larger trained model's outputs (also called a teacher model) during training, instead of simply the ground truth [11]. This technique was used for training the segmentation models. The same technique was applied to the detection model. The teacher model overfitted, likely because of the low number of boats in the training dataset. As a result, the traditional training method was used for the smaller detection models.

The average time taken for convergence of the various models are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Details about the training of the different models

Use Case	# of elements in dataset*	Time taken to convergence (in epochs)	Time taken to convergence (in days)
Boat segmentation (Teacher)	11k	900	2
Boat segmentation (Student)	11k	1400	3
Cloud segmentation (Teacher)	70k	500	1.5
Cloud segmentation (Student)	70k	800	2.5
Boat detection	11k	800	2.5

*This counts the number of cropped tiles, and not the number of large images.

Once the model is ready, it is quantized and compiled using Vitis AI to be deployed on-board as a shared object. Having the model as a shared object meant that the neural networks could be updated without modifying the executable described in the next section.

ON-BOARD EXECUTION

The compiled model only handles the core inference, i.e. the generation of predictions for a given input. A wrapper is required to oversee the scheduling, pre-processing and to interpret the inference output. This handler was implemented in C++. A single C++ executable was designed to handle all three use cases. The use case for an execution is selected using input arguments.

The CPU handles the transfer of the image data to the DPU. Each MonoScape100 image (4k x 3k pixels) has a size of 12 megabytes since each pixel value is stored as a signed 8-bit integer. During inference, depending on the model architecture, the memory required can be several orders of magnitude greater than the image used as input to the neural network, thus much greater than 12 megabytes. The memory available to deploy a model on the DPU was limited to 64 megabytes. The image had to be processed in tiles. This leads to another issue: the prediction around the tile edges would not be smooth and may introduce artifacts when producing the final output mask for segmentation for example. Also, tiles are processed sequentially. More tiles imply a longer execution. To minimise the negative effects of tiling, the tiles must be of the largest size which can fit in the DPU memory. For the segmentation use cases, the maximum tile size was 352x352 pixels. For detection, the input tile size was already fixed to 300x300 as a requirement for the network architecture, and this size fit in the DPU memory. So, no further adjustment was required. To reduce tiling artifacts, overlapping can be used. This means that the areas in the image which are close to the tile edges appear in multiple tiles, and their prediction is averaged to produce the overall result.

The input must also be processed before feeding it to the DPU. For this mission, there were two steps in preprocessing. The first involved a division by the largest possible value of the image (255 since each pixel was represented by an unsigned 8-bit integer), to produce an image with values between 0 and 1 for normalisation purposes. Secondly, the imaging pixels deteriorate over time and produce salt-and-pepper noise. This led to some false positives during inference. Neural networks are generally robust to this type of noise. However, in this case, there were not enough recent images used during training. Therefore, a list of defective pixels was generated by performing statistical analysis on the available images and by using the calibration frames (flat frames and dark frames). In flight, a filter was applied to replace the listed pixels by the median of its closest neighbouring pixels. A median filter was favoured over a mean filter, since median filters do not introduce any new, and thus potentially impossible, values, unlike mean filters. Both operations were done by the CPU.

Finally, the CPU was also responsible for processing the DPU output. The raw output of a neural network is not human-readable. As described earlier, for the segmentation use cases, masks of the same size as the original image are produced. In our case, the mask is binary: for each pixel, it shows whether the object of interest is present or not. For detection, since the architecture is inspired from the SSD, the predicted outputs must be filtered to remove redundant boxes and boxes with a low confidence score. The masks are saved as image files, while the coordinates of the detection boxes are saved in a CSV file.

RESULTS

Scores Before Upload

As described in the dataset preparation section, the DNN was improved over the mission’s duration as more images were obtained and labelled. Each new model was evaluated on its corresponding version of the dataset, containing both simulated and real images. The early results of training were promising, with F1-scores greater than 80%. These are summarised in the table below:

It is important to note that the F1-scores for different versions of a particular use case, in **Table 2**, cannot be directly compared. This is because they were not evaluated on the same dataset, due to it being continuously updated. This was seen especially for the boat segmentation model, where the more recent model had a worse F1-score at the time of training than the first version, while the actual predictions on-board were better. More recent F1-scores are more reliable since the later datasets contain more real images. This means that an improving F1-score is a good sign, but a fairer comparison must be done by evaluating the models on the same dataset. This is explained in the next section.

Table 2 F1-scores of the uploaded models

Use Case	Version	F1-score (%)
Boat detection	V0	80
Boat detection	V1	85
Boat detection	V2	88
Boat segmentation	V0	92
Boat segmentation	V1	88
Cloud segmentation	V0	82
Cloud segmentation	V1	92
Cloud segmentation	V2	94

End-of-Mission Analysis

We previously saw that the F1-scores during training were promising. However, the results of the first executions we received did not match those numbers. Early iterations, especially those trained on datasets with more simulated images than images from the MonoScape100, presented many false positives, especially on land. Bright rectangular spots in the middle of large fields were detected as boats for example. For clouds, early versions confused sea foam with cloudy patches. To quantify the evolution of the neural networks, the latter were all evaluated on a test dataset which did not contain any simulated image. The final F1-scores are given in **Table 3**.

Table 3 F1-scores of different versions of each model on the final test dataset

Use Case	Version	Dataset composition	Final F1-score (%)
Boat detection	V0	Simulated only	2.6
Boat detection	V1	Simulated + a few real	4.3
Boat detection	V2	Simulated + Real	86
Boat segmentation	V0	Simulated	16
Boat segmentation	V1	Simulated + Real	76
Cloud segmentation	V0	Simulated only	71
Cloud segmentation	V1	Simulated + Real	89
Cloud segmentation	V2	Real only	90

The addition of real images greatly improves the results. For boats, the first versions which were trained on simulated images mainly, performed poorly when tested on images from the actual sensor, despite the efforts to reproduce the radiometric characteristics. On the other hand, the predictions of the first version of the cloud use case already had an F1-score greater than 70%. This is because thick clouds are often large, saturated patches which are easier to distinguish from the rest of the image.

The fact that the scores in **Table 3** are very different than those in **Table 2**, indicates that the initial datasets were not representative of the final on-board images. More work needs to be done to improve on domain adaptation. This can be done by developing a complete simulation model of the sensor or by making the models less sensitive to the sensor’s specific radiometry, by using “extreme” augmentations during the training steps.

In terms of execution duration, the detection execution was faster at a rate of 30 seconds per image, while the segmentation execution required just under 70 seconds. They both had a peak power usage of about 2W.

There were around 1700 executions over a 4-month period, with the majority run in the later half to maximise the number of outputs with the most improved DNNs.

This is summarised in **Table 4**.

Table 4 Executions per use case

Use Case	# of executions	Duration per execution	Throughput (pixels/s)
Boat segmentation	609	70	180k
Boat detection	627	30	419k
Cloud segmentation	459	70	180k

There were more executions for the use cases around boats instead of cloud, since boats were rarer.

We can see that, for boats, the detection use case is more interesting for several reasons. It is faster and requires less memory than the segmentation use case. The final F1-score is also greater for detection. The only downside is that its post-processing is often more complex.

Prediction Examples

Figure 1 shows examples of predictions obtained for the three use cases. For visualisation purposes, the on-board outputs (mask for segmentation, bounding box coordinates for detection) are overlaid on the original image. For the bounding box, the confidence score (0.982) is also displayed.

Boat segmentation and detection

Cloud segmentation

Figure 1 Prediction examples of the different models

IMPROVEMENTS

Since the end of the mission, Agenium Space has continued to improve the on-board software. Notable improvements include a higher throughput by using alternative neural network architectures and newer versions of the various tools used during the mission. The latest Vitis AI tools are more efficient at handling operations required by neural networks. This, combined with custom architectures which require fewer operations and read/write instructions, significantly improves the overall throughput, without degrading the predictions. As an example, we now have segmentation models which have a raw throughput – a throughput measured without taking into account the loading of an image – of up to 20M pixels/s (2M px/s/W), and detection models with a raw throughput of up to 25M pixels/s (2.5M px/s/W) on a Zynq UltraScale+ board, with an average power consumption of 10W. As an example, this means that for the given use cases (clouds and boats), information could be extracted from a 40k-by-40k Pléiades image in under 80 seconds!

We have also expanded our pre-processing toolbox with the addition of pattern noise correction, namely noise from two sources: photo-response non-uniformity and dark signal non-uniformity. This improves the quality of the image and can improve the AI inference on images with a low signal-to-noise ratio. This is currently done on CPU, but the goal is to have the option to offload this task to the FPGA, if there is sufficient logic available alongside the DPU cores, to improve the overall throughput if the tasks on the CPU are the bottleneck.

CONCLUSION

This mission was a huge success for both partners on various aspects. For Agenium Space, it demonstrated the ability to generate high performance AI models for a constrained environment that was already in orbit. It also showed the capacity to continuously improve an existing network throughout a mission. The importance of proper datasets was also showcased for Earth Observation use-cases. On Loft Orbital's side, through this mission, the integration of an AI application post-launch and the creation of an autonomous pipeline was demonstrated. Thanks to this successful collaboration, Agenium Space and Loft Orbital have decided to work on other similar projects in the foreseeable future. The work done throughout this mission shows promising results for the future of NewSpace.

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